

Understanding the effect of saliva composition depending on gender and age on wine aroma perception: oral aroma release, dynamics of sensory perception and consumer preferences and liking

Celia Criado, María Pérez-Jiménez, Carolina Muñoz-González and MARIA ANGELES POZO-BAYÓN

Instituto de Investigación en Ciencias de la Alimentación (CIAL) (CSIC-UAM) C/Nicolás Cabrera, 9, 28049, Madrid (Spain), m.delpozo@csic.es

Abstract

In order to determine the relationship between saliva composition depending on age and gender on wine oral aroma release and the impact this might have on aroma perception over consumption and on consumer preferences and liking, a large study comprising three different approaches was performed based on (a) determining oral aroma release during wine intake; (b) rating the perceived retronasal aroma intensity over wine consumption by time-intensity assays and (c) checking the consumer's hedonic and emotional response to wines. Participants belonged to two different age groups (younger (18-35 y.o.) and seniors (>55 y.o)) and they were gendered balanced. Their saliva samples were collected in order to relate saliva composition to instrumental and sensory measurements. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) on aroma release and aroma perception between age-gender groups were found, which also depended on the wine type. Total protein content and salivary flow were the two salivary parameters more related with this. Additionally, differences in some emotional response among groups were found, which will be explored in future works in the aim to elaborate more personalised wines for target consumers in order to increase their acceptance of wine.

Keywords: wine, retronasal aroma release, saliva, aroma perception, consumer hedonic and emotional response

Introduction

Spain is the third largest wine producer country in Europe, behind France and Italy [1], however, the consumption of wine compared to other alcoholic beverages (such as beer or spirits) is considerably lower in Spain (28 %) compared to France (59%) or Italy (65%). Indeed, the consumption of wine in the Spanish households has decreased by over 60% in the last two decades [2]. Additionally, a large difference in wine consumption patterns depending on age has been also noticed. While seniors (55 years and above) consume more than 73 % (total litres of wine consumed in households), the consumption of youngsters (under 35 years old) is clearly lower (4.5 %) [3].

Furthermore, differences in wine liking and emotions considering a group of consumers of different ages have recently been observed [4]. Interestingly, a relationship between wine liking, emotions and sensory characteristics have also been shown [5]. Therefore, although the reasons driving wine consumption could be of different nature and linked to intrinsic factors (e.g. label, wine name, shape of the bottle, etc.), there is certainly an impact of wine sensory characteristics on consumer's choice that are directly dependent on the wine chemical composition.

In this sense, aroma has been one of the most important sensory attributes for driving consumer's preference and choice, and although the olfactory cues can give us an idea or expectation of wine liking, wine acceptability and the repeated purchase of a wine can be only assessed during wine tasting. During wine intake, aroma molecules are released in the oral and throat cavities where they can interact with saliva. Different effects such as aroma dilution, interaction with proteins or even metabolism have been described in the literature, which might affect the amount and type of the aroma molecules that could finally reach the olfactory receptors, therefore with a putative effect on aroma intensity and aroma quality [6].

On the other hand, different works have also shown that saliva composition can change through lifespan [7]. This invites us to hypothesize that changes in saliva composition depending on age could also affect aroma release and perception and therefore wine aroma liking.

Therefore, the aim of this work has been to evaluate the effect of saliva composition depending on age (and gender) on wine oral aroma release, aroma perception over consumption and on consumer's preference (hedonic and emotional response).

Experimental

Three independent studies aimed at determining (a) oral aroma release during wine intake, (b) aroma intensity over wine consumption and (c) the consumer's hedonic and emotional response to wine were performed. In all of them, saliva samples were collected and their composition determined. All the participants in this study received pertinent information about it and they signed the approval consent for their participation. The Bioethical Committee of the Spanish National Council of Research (CSIC) also approved the experimental procedure. The experimental approaches are described here in.

Oral aroma release during wine intake

For this study, 32 individuals belonging to two different age groups: younger (<35 y.o.) and senior (>55 y.o.) were recruited and grouped accordingly to their age-gender in: (YF) Young-Female (n=8), (YM) Young-Male (n=8); (SF) Senior-Female (n=7); (SM) Senior-Male (n=9). Stimulated saliva was collected before the assays and pH, salivary flow, viscosity, minerals (Zn, Na, K, Ca, Mg), total protein content (TPC), and some enzymatic activities (total salivary esterase activity (TSEA) and α -amylase) were determined using procedures previously described [8]. For this study we used two types of wines, a red one and a white one. To monitor oral aroma release we used the in mouth Head Space Stir Bar Sorptive extraction followed by GC-MS analysis (in mouth-HS SBSE-GC-MS) as previously described [9]. The procedure consisted in a gentle mouth rinsing with the wine for 30 s, and three in-mouth samplings after spatting the wine off: immediately (0 s), at 60 s and at 120 s. Each sampling was for 30 s with a different twister. All the analyses were done in triplicates. Before each sampling, the oral cavity was also sampled to check for the absence of typical wine volatiles. All the twistors were desorbed in the TDU and trapped in the CIS of the GC-MS in the conditions described by Pérez-Jiménez and Pozo-Bayón [9] to build the release curves of each volatile compound identified in the mouth.

Aroma intensity over wine consumption

This study aimed to know if there were also differences on aroma perception between age groups over wine consumption. For this, we recruited 22 volunteers from both genders, eleven were from the senior group (> 55 y.o.) and the other eleven were young individuals (between 18 and 35 years old). Although most of them already participated in the first study (n=18), four new participants belonging to the younger group were exclusively recruited for this study. Two wines, a red and a white wine, were used. In previous trials, some characteristic wine aroma attributes, such as apple and pineapple in the white wine; and smoky and black pepper in the red wine were selected for the Time-Intensity (T-I) study. Before the sample analysis, volunteers were trained in the recognition of the selected aroma descriptors and in the T-I methodology by using tablets and the Compusense software. For the sensory evaluation, volunteers rated the variation in the intensity of the above mentioned attributes over 2 minutes after wine intake and expectoration (15 mL). T-I parameters (Imax, TImax, Tend and AUC) were extracted from the T-I curve and they were correlated with salivary parameters. For the latest, the same procedure already described was employed and the salivary composition was also determined [10].

Consumer's hedonic and emotional response to wine

For this study we recruited 105 consumers, 45 of them were seniors and 58 of them were within the younger group. Two wines, a red and a white wine with *black pepper* and *pineapple* notes as dominant descriptors, respectively, were used for this study. Consumer tests were performed by using the Compusense software. Volunteers were asked to rate aroma intensity, wine liking and their emotional response considering 15 emotional terms from the lexicon recently published for the Spanish wine consumer [5]. A saliva sample was always collected prior to the sensory test as previously described [10]. Two measurements, salivary flow and total protein content were performed in this sample, since they were the most correlated salivary parameters to aroma perception from the T-I study [10].

Results and discussion

In order to determine the relationship between age and oral aroma release during wine intake, the oral aroma release after wine tasting was assessed at three different times, immediately, 60 s and 120 s after wine expectoration using a white and a red wine. A total of 24 and 23 aroma compounds were identified in the oral cavity after the white and red wine intake, respectively. After application of different statistical tests (ANOVA and stepwise linear discriminant analysis) it was possible to confirm differences in oral aroma release among the four age-gender groups (YF, YM, SF, SM), which also depended on the aroma compound and wine type. These results can be shown in the PCA depicted in Figure 1, where it is also possible to check the relationship between oral aroma release and saliva composition. As it can be seen, the higher release of furanic compounds and C13-norisoprenoids in senior groups after red wine tasting could be related to some differences in their saliva

composition (higher TPC and α -amylase activity). On the contrary, the effect of gender on aroma release was larger in younger individuals. YM group showed a higher release of esters and alcohols regardless the type of wine (white and red) (Figure 1). On the contrary, the YF group showed the lowest oral aroma release in both wines from the four age-gender groups; but this did not seem to be explained by saliva composition. Overall, differences in oral aroma release among gender groups were more evident in younger than in seniors.

Figure 1: Graphical projection of the two firsts components obtained after the application of PCA to oral aroma release data after white wine (a) and red wine tasting (b) and saliva composition in the four age-gender groups. Only those variables that showed significant differences among groups ($p < 0.05$) have been included. For each age-gender groups only the centroids are represented.

The results from the T-I study also revealed differences in aroma perception depending on the age. Interestingly, results only showed an effect of the age group in the intensity perception of the two aroma attributes in the red wine (smoky and black pepper aroma) but not in the perception of any of the aroma attributes considered in the white wine (apple and pineapple). In the red wine significant differences ($p < 0.005$) in most parameters extracted from the T-I curve (Imax, Tend and AUC) were found. For instance, senior individuals showed the highest values of Imax, Tend and AUC of smoky aroma (Figure 2). Similar results were found for black pepper and the highest Tend and AUC values were found in senior compared to the younger individuals. These results are in agreement with the higher oral aroma release of certain compounds (e.g methyl fufural, furfural) in the senior group in the previous study (Figure 1), which might be associated to these aroma attributes in red wines. Additionally, the Pearson correlation analysis showed that the salivary total protein content (that was significantly higher in the senior group) was positively and significantly related to Imax (0.406) while the salivary flow (significantly lower in the senior compared to the younger group) was negatively related to Imax (-0.444).

Figure 2: T-I profile (average values) for the smoky aroma rated by senior and younger participants.

Finally, results from the consumer study also showed an impact of the age-gender groups, but only in the black pepper attribute in red wine. Nonetheless, there was no significant effect in the perceived intensity of pineapple aroma (Figure 3). Interestingly, senior women rated the lowest aroma intensity of black pepper, which is not in agreement with results from the T-I, in which seniors showed the highest perception of smoky and black pepper aroma. Nonetheless, differences in the type of volunteers, trained in the case of T-I, or untrained

consumers, more focused on hedonics than in descriptive traits, could be the reason for this disparity, which has also been noticed in previous studies [11].

Figure 3: Scores of the pineapple and pepper intensity in the red wine considering the four age-gender groups of consumers.

Interestingly, the salivary analysis in such large population was quite in agreement with previous results, and seniors showed the highest TPC and senior women the lowest salivary flow. On the contrary, younger men showed the highest salivary flow and lowest TPC. The Pearson correlation analysis also revealed some interesting facts. For instance, a positive and significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between black pepper aroma and salivary flow (0.218) and between liking and TPC (0.211) was found. This result could be related to the intensity of the astringency perceived by the consumer (that was not measured in this study), which is often linked with lower wine acceptability. This sensation is associated with the capacity of tannins to bind some salivary proteins, which can affect the oral mucosal pellicle reducing the lubricity of the oral cavity. However, if the total protein content is higher there could be still salivary proteins to keep this lubricity and therefore, the astringency perceived should be lower [12]. Nonetheless, this hypothesis should be confirmed in further studies, which also must include the score of this orosensory perception.

Regarding the emotional response, which could provide additional information to liking, there were only significant differences by age-gender groups in one of the 15 emotional terms. Specifically, the emotion *curious* was rated with the lowest intensity in the case of senior women and only in red wines. Some other differences in the emotional response were also found, depending on the wine type. For instance *nostalgic* was higher in red wines, while *refreshed* was higher in white wines. On the other hand, and interestingly, a positive correlation between liking and positive emotions was confirmed. Some examples of these emotions included *satisfied* (0.70), *joyful* (0.54), *desirous* (0.54), *lucky* (0.53) and *cheerful* (0.51) among others. On the contrary, correlations with liking were negative for negative emotions such as *displeased* (-0.46), *sadness* (-0.25), or *sleepy* (-0.22).

Conclusions

Overall, this study has confirmed differences in aroma release and aroma perception between age-gender groups, which were more pronounced during red wine than during white wine consumption. Additionally, saliva composition, and specifically salivary total protein content and flow (which were inversely related) were related to aroma release and perception in a compound dependent manner. Finally, the age-gender groups also had an effect on consumer's aroma perception in red wines, but it did not affect the liking. Nonetheless, a positive correlation between red wine liking and salivary total protein content was found. Finally, the differences found in the emotional response in some groups (senior-women, younger-women), could be interesting for targeting new types of products, able to elicit specific positive emotions in these consumer groups increasing their acceptance of wine.

References

1. OIV. OIV assessment of the world wine situation. 2019 [Press release].
2. OeMv. Consumption of wine and other beverages in the Spanish food channel. 2018. Retrieved from www.oemv.es.
3. MAPA. Annual Food Consumption Report in Spain 2018. 2019. Retrieved from www.mapa.gob.es: <http://publicacionesoficiales.boe.es>
4. Mora, M., Urdaneta, E., & Chaya, C. Emotional response to wine: Sensory properties, age and gender as drivers of consumers' preferences. *Food Qual. Prefer.* 2018;66:19-28.
5. Mora, M., de Matos, A. D., Fernández-Ruiz, V., Briz, T., Chaya, C. Comparison of methods to develop an emotional lexicon of wine: Conventional vs Rapid-method approach. *Food Qual. Pref.* 2020;83:10392
6. Muñoz-González, C., Feron, G., Canon, F. Main effects of human saliva on flavour perception and the potential contribution to food consumption. *Proc. Nutr. Soc.* 2018;77(4):423-431.

7. Muñoz-González, C., Feron, G., & Canon, F. Physiological and oral parameters contribute prediction of retronasal aroma release in an elderly cohort. *Food Chem.* 2021;342:128355.
8. Criado, C., Chaya, C., Fernández-Ruiz, V., Álvarez, M. D., Herranz, B., Pozo-Bayón, M. Á. Effect of saliva composition and flow on inter-individual differences in the temporal perception of retronasal aroma during wine tasting. *Food Res. Int.* 2019;126:108677.
9. Pérez-Jiménez, M., Pozo-Bayón, M. Á. Development of an in-mouth headspace sorptive extraction method (HSSE) for oral aroma monitoring and application to wines of different chemical composition. *Food Res. Int.* 2019;121:97-107.
10. Criado, C., Muñoz-González, C., & Pozo-Bayón, M. Á. Differences in salivary flow and composition between age groups are correlated to dynamic retronasal aroma perception during wine consumption. *Food Qual. Pref.* 2021;87:104046.
11. Sáenz-Navajas, M. P., Avizcuri, J. M., Ballester, J., Fernández-Zurbano, P., Ferreira, V., Peyron, D., & Valentin, D. Sensory-active compounds influencing wine experts' and consumers' perception of red wine intrinsic quality. *LWT.* 2015;60(1):400-411.
12. Crawford, C. R., & Running, C. A. Addition of chocolate milk to diet corresponds to protein concentration changes in human saliva. *Physiol. Behav.* 2020;225:113080.